

Sensitivity of L-band Radar Backscatter to Forest Biomass in Semi-arid Environments: A Comparative Analysis of Parametric and Non-Parametric Models

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of frequently used parametric and non-parametric models for biomass retrieval from L-band radar backscatter. Two areas, one in Spain and one in Australia, characterized by different tree species, forest structure and field sampling designs were selected to demonstrate that retrieval error metrics are similar for different local conditions and sampling characteristics. A mixed-model retrieval strategy was proposed to reduce the overall (i.e., across the entire biomass range) as well as by biomass interval errors.

Significant relationships were found between above-ground biomass and radar backscatter with most of the backscatter dynamic range being limited to a fairly low range of biomass values (< 30 t/ha) in both study areas. Biomass retrieval errors were largely similar for all parametric and non-parametric models tested. However, some parametric models consistently provided lower correlation between observed and predicted biomass while non-parametric models generally provided an unbiased estimation. A mixed-model retrieval strategy was shown to reduce biomass estimation errors by up to 15%.

Biomass retrieval errors were highly variable within the L-band sensitivity interval suggesting that overall accuracy estimates should be used with care especially for low biomass intervals (<30 t/ha) where surface scattering could dominate the total backscatter. Despite exhibiting the highest dynamic range, low biomass areas were characterized by the highest estimation errors (in excess of 80%). Conversely, relative estimation errors were as low as 20-35% for the 30-75 t/ha biomass intervals while at higher biomass levels the estimation error increased due to signal saturation.

I. Introduction

Retrieval of forest characteristics is currently one of the main research topics of the remote sensing community with accurate estimation of carbon emissions from deforestation and forest degradation

being a major challenge. Forest carbon stock estimation is a sensitive research topic since information on forest spatial distribution, biomass levels and dynamics is needed for greenhouse gases flux estimation, and thus policy development and implementation [1].

The last two decades have been strongly focused on the extraction of biomass estimates from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) sensors after relationships between forest biomass and radar backscatter coefficients were demonstrated more than three decades ago [2]. Global coverage, high temporal and spatial resolutions, and independence from cloud cover were the main attractive features of space-borne SAR sensors. The sensitivity of SAR backscatter to biomass levels depends mostly on system wavelength, with P-band (around 64 cm wavelength) recognized early on as the most sensitive due to its greater penetration of the vegetation [3-6]. However, most recent research was focused on L-band due to the availability of such data from the Japanese Earth Resources Satellite (JERS) and Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR). The potential for using L-band radar backscatter to estimate above-ground biomass has been studied for most forest types, ranging from boreal to tropical regions using airborne and/or space borne sensors [6-14]. The consensus amongst such studies is that backscatter coefficients increase with biomass until a saturation point is reached which is influenced by forest type/structure and environmental conditions (i.e., rainfall, freeze/thaw cycles, etc), as well as sensor characteristics such as wavelength and polarization. The observed saturation point is usually between 30 to 100 t/ha across most forest types and radar polarizations [3, 5, 9, 15]. Previous studies also showed that L-band cross-polarized radar backscatter was more sensitive to variations in biomass [3, 16, 17], whereas co-polarized backscatter showed greater sensitivity to differences in forest cover fraction. The dynamic range (i.e., the difference between maximum and minimum backscatter values recorded for different vegetation densities) has been seen to vary between 4-10 dB for L-band cross-polarized data [11, 17]. Most of this dynamic range, however, covers only a relatively small biomass span, usually below 50 t/ha. For the remaining biomass range up to the saturation point the backscatter increase is modest, frequently within 2-3 dB which could hinder retrieval algorithms [9, 11, 15, 18-21]. A number of biomass retrieval strategies have emerged, the majority of which were based on parametric (i.e.,

empirical and semi-empirical) models. Relating radar backscatter to above-ground biomass (AGB) using empirical models was achieved with a range of functional forms, including linear [8, 17, 20, 22], logarithmic [23], exponential [18, 23] and higher degree polynomials [3]. In addition, some empirical models were parameterized for backscatter estimation as a function of biomass through sigmoid type functions [12, 24] and subsequently inverted to recover AGB. The semi-empirical models [14, 25, 26] were frequently based on the water cloud model [27] and the radiative transfer theory. Finally, some authors have used numerical [28, 29] or non-parametric models [30] to estimate biomass levels.

Past studies have demonstrated the high variability of error in radar predicted biomass with respect to the actual (i.e., field assessed) values. In [5], errors between 39% and 75% were found in boreal forests depending on the exclusion/inclusion of older stands. In pine forest stands [8] obtained an average error in the order of 59 t/ha which translates into an error of approximately 80% for forests with average biomass of 75 t/ha; the inclusion of all stands further increased the error. Sandberg et al. [17] estimated biomass in a boreal forest with errors reaching 36-46% of the mean biomass values. In contrast, relatively low errors (25%) were obtained by [14] in boreal forests, but only when highly homogeneous stands were used. Such studies have reported extensively on the relationship between radar backscatter and forests biomass, but typically for forests with biomass levels well above the L-band saturation point [12, 13, 31], and only occasionally within the sensitivity interval [11, 22]. Consequently, the retrieved biomass intervals were usually much larger than the acknowledged L-band range for biomass sensitivity, making it difficult to assess the retrieval accuracy within those limits. Moreover, limited information is available on the variability of retrieval errors by biomass intervals, which can greatly influence model selection depending on the specific application and forest biomass distribution frequency.

While many studies have been conducted in boreal, temperate and tropical environments, fewer studies have focused their attention on low biomass forests in semi-arid environments. All studies carried out in semi-arid forests used empirical models with no author using more physically based modeling approaches [32-35]. Dry conditions are known to enhance wave penetration depth due to

decreased vegetation water content, allowing for higher interaction of radar waves with the ground surface and thus different scattering mechanisms. In addition, the rate of backscatter increase with biomass is lower in open forests (often the case of semi-arid forests) when compared to closed canopy forests [36]. Although, semi-arid forests frequently present lower biomass levels, which should theoretically yield an increase in the overall estimation accuracy, variations of the surface scattering component (through soil moisture and roughness) could result in similar backscatter levels for a variety of biomass/surface conditions especially for co-polarized waves [28, 36] which could hinder biomass retrieval.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the accuracy of different parametric and non-parametric models for biomass retrieval from L-band ALOS PALSAR backscatter data and to demonstrate that by biomass interval estimation errors depend little on species composition, forest structure or field sampling design. The specific objectives were: i) to assess the backscatter/biomass relationships for forests characterized by average biomass levels well below the L-band saturation point, ii) to observe the effectiveness of a range of parametric and non-parametric models for biomass retrieval, iii) to study the influence of biomass levels on the retrieval accuracy and, iv) to propose a retrieval strategy that reduces the overall biomass retrieval error (i.e., across the entire biomass range) as well as the error for individual biomass intervals.

II. Study areas and datasets

2.1 Field datasets

Field data were available for two study areas corresponding to regional and local forest inventories. At the regional level, the analysis was focused on semi-arid pine forests located in the central sector of the Iberian range, Teruel, Spain. The pine species present in the Teruel region were *Pinus sylvestris*, *Pinus halepensis*, *Pinus nigra*, and *Pinus pinaster*. The field work was conducted between December 2004 and April 2005 within the framework of the 3rd Spanish Forest National Inventory (FNI). The sampling grid followed a regular pattern with one sample plot every kilometer within forested areas. All trees with a diameter at breast height (DBH) greater than 7.5 cm were recorded for

their DBH and height. The plot radius depended on the maximal DBH at each location: 5 m radius when the maximum DBH was below 12.5 cm, 10 m radius when the maximum DBH was between 12.5 cm and 25.5 cm, 15 m radius when the maximum DBH was between 25.5 cm and 42.5 cm and, 25 m radius when the maximum DBH was above 42.5 cm. The radius of 50% of the 134 plots used in this study (Fig.1) was 15 m, with approximately 25% of the plots having a smaller radius (i.e., 10 m) and 25% of the plots having a larger radius (i.e., 25m). Only plots located on flat or near flat areas (slope $\leq 5^\circ$) were selected so that results could be easily compared with those from the second study area which is characterized by a nearly flat topography. Moreover, working on flat areas avoided the effect of sloped terrain on biomass retrieval [37] which according to recent tomographical experiments [38] could enhance the double bounce effect especially for co-polarized waves (i.e., HH). The total AGB was calculated for each tree using species-specific allometric equations [39] and aggregated for each plot. The AGB for the selected plots varied between 2.2 and 127.2 t/ha with over 95% of them having an AGB below 100 t/ha. The mean plot biomass was 32.0 t/ha with a standard deviation of ± 26.6 t/ha. The mean tree height was 8.4m ± 2.6 m with individual heights varying between 2m and 20m.

At the local level, the analysis was focused on the Gillenbah forest (1600 ha) located in New South Wales, Australia where the dominant forest species is white cypress pine (*Calitris glucophylla*) while grey box (*Eucalyptus microcarpa*) is disseminated throughout the forest and accounts for only 10% of the trees. In September 2011 a biometric survey was conducted using 60 plots (500m² each) clustered in 12 sites (Fig.1). A cluster site consisted of a centre plot with four surrounding plots spaced at a distance of 35 m in the cardinal directions. The circumference and height of all trees with DBH greater than 5 cm was recorded whereas smaller trees were counted and their height was estimated plot-wise as being the most frequent height (i.e., smaller trees were largely even-aged). Information on grass surface cover and average height from 10 sparsely vegetated plots was also collected. The total above-ground biomass was calculated for each tree using species-specific allometric equations [40, 41] and aggregated at plot level.

[Fig. 1 about here]

The forest type over the two study areas was comparable (i.e., largely coniferous species) with average biomass levels well inside the established sensitivity interval for the L-band radar backscatter. However, some differences were noted mostly with respect to the higher biomass levels over the Australian study area and the larger variety of tree species present in the Spanish study area which was not surprising given the latter's much larger extent. Such differences were not viewed as an impediment but rather as an enhancement of this study since our goal was to assess if similar trends and biomass estimation accuracies are obtained regardless of field sampling design and forest structure. It is also noted that for the Spanish study area the minimum DBH recorded was slightly higher (i.e., 7.5 vs. 5 cm) and no information on regrowth was available thereby suggesting a certain underestimation of the actual biomass values.

2.2 Radar datasets

Several dual-polarized (HH and HV) ALOS PALSAR scenes were available for each study area (Table 1). The satellite images, acquired within one to three years of the ground data collection, were multi-looked in both range (4) and azimuth (16) to obtain similar ground pixel spacing (50m). The intensity was transformed to the radar backscatter coefficient (σ^0) after applying the absolute calibration factors [42]. To further reduce speckle noise the multi-looked images were filtered using a 3x3 window [43]. Due to the rough topography, in the Spanish study area, the backscatter intensity was normalized for the varying incidence angle and the effective pixel area [44] using a 20-m spatial resolution digital elevation model (DEM) obtained from the regional government of Aragón. This DEM was assessed as accurate within ± 2.5 m horizontally and ± 5 m vertically. After correction, the gamma nought (γ^0) images only included variations of the scattering properties of the target. Note that for a flat topography, as was the case for the Australian study site, sigma and gamma nought are equal. Therefore, backscatter normalization was not carried out for the Australian dataset. All images were geocoded to the UTM coordinate system using a lookup table that described the transformation between the radar and the map geometry [45]. The lookup table was generated using the DEM and the orbital information of the radar data. To correct for possible inaccuracies in the input data, a

refinement of the lookup table was applied, in the form of offsets between each SAR image and a reference image (e.g., a DEM based simulated SAR image) transformed to the radar geometry.

[Table 1 about here]

Although there was a certain interval between field data collection and satellite image acquisition no correction was applied to compensate for tree growth. For the Australian study area the acquisition gap was less than 18 months which meant negligible growth especially in such semi-arid environments. For the Spanish study area the acquisition gap was 30 to 42 months. However, according to the third Spanish FNI, the annual average net change in timber volume for pine species in the Teruel region over the past decade was $2.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ (i.e., approximately 1 t/ha). Although timber volume is not equivalent to total biomass, such small changes suggest either low annual AGB increments or quasi-equilibrium between tree growth and tree mortality.

2.3 Data extraction

For the Spanish dataset the backscatter coefficient was extracted for the pixel containing the center of each ground sampling plot (0.25 ha) which corresponds to the location of the 1 km UTM grid nodes. Such relatively small areas were used to restrain the extraction to the area actually sampled on the ground since no ancillary data were available for the highly fragmented Spanish landscape.

For comparability reasons (i.e., similar speckle noise) the same plot size had to be used to extract the backscatter at the Australian study area. However, the field assessed plots were much smaller (i.e., 0.05 ha) while forest spatial variability was high. Assigning the field assessed biomass to a 0.25 ha area centered at each plot would have resulted in a noisier backscatter/biomass relationship. In addition, due to the close proximity of the plots within each cluster site the 0.25 ha areas would have overlapped. To circumvent such limitations a reference biomass map was produced using a high point density (40 p m^{-1}) lidar dataset from a concurrent with the ground sampling flight. The relationship between field plots (i.e., 60 forests and 10 sparse vegetation) and gridded lidar metrics (i.e., pulse density of the 1-12 m height stratum, canopy percent cover in the 6-8 m height stratum, and the volume under the forest canopy surface) were used within multiple linear regressions to model AGB

as a function of the lidar metrics. The parameterized model was subsequently applied to obtain a spatially explicit biomass map for the Australian study area. More details on biomass modeling from lidar data are given in [46]. At plot level (i.e., 0.05 ha), the AGB retrieval from lidar point cloud data was accurate within 17.2 t/ha (28% relative). However, when analyzed by cluster site (i.e., 0.25 ha) the retrieval error was significantly lower, -- i.e., as small as 14% relative to the ground estimates. Biomass values extracted from this biomass reference map were subsequently used for modeling.

A random grid of 131 plots (0.25 ha) was used to extract the radar backscatter and the lidar based reference biomass over the Australian study area (Fig. 1). The AGB for the selected random plots varied between 1.5 and 145.6 t/ha with over 95% of them being below 100 t/ha. The mean plot biomass was 50.1 t/ha with a standard deviation of ± 26.5 t/ha. The mean tree height over the Australian study site was $7.2\text{m} \pm 2.5\text{m}$ with individual heights varying between 2m and 32.5m.

III. Methods

A number of modeling approaches can be used to study the relationships between biomass and radar backscatter and to retrieve biomass (i.e., numerical, parametric and non-parametric modeling). Since numerical modeling requires detailed description of surface properties (soil roughness and moisture) and vegetation characteristics (leaf/branch orientation, thickness, water content, etc.) to estimate backscatter and such information was not collected during the forest inventory campaigns the analysis was restricted to parametric and non-parametric models. Although previous studies showed that using multiple polarizations does not significantly improve biomass estimation error [17, 35] it was decided to test not only single polarized but also multi-polarized parametric and non-parametric models to corroborate such results over semi-arid, low biomass forests.

3.1 Analysis of the backscatter-biomass relationship

The relationship between radar backscatter was studied as a function of biomass levels using descriptive statistics (i.e., mean and standard deviation of the mean). In addition, the backscatter saturation point with increasing biomass as well as the biomass density below saturation was computed as an average for all available datasets at each study area as proposed in [12]. The

backscatter saturation point (linear units) corresponds exactly to the coefficient a of the model (see next section model 2). A 1 dB below the saturation point was considered by [12] as indicative of the maximum retrievable biomass taking into account uncertainties in sensor calibration and sample size. In this study, however, the maximum retrievable biomass was computed for 0.5 dB below saturation since uncertainty of PALSAR backscatter measurements is smaller and the spatial resolution higher (i.e., lower speckle noise for the same ground resolution) when compared to JERS data.

3.2 Biomass retrieval from parametric and non-parametric models

Six parametric and three non-parametric models were used to retrieve biomass and evaluate the estimation errors. In this paper, the parametric models were further categorized into forward and backward models to distinguish between model parameterization/biomass retrieval strategies. Forward models parameterize the response in backscatter with increasing biomass hence minimizing the errors of the response variable backscatter. After parameterization the biomass is estimated using an inverse function. Conversely, in backward models, the AGB is expressed as a function of backscatter without the need of additional functions.

3.2.1. Forward parametric models

The three forward parametric models used (eq. 1 to 3) were based on the radiative transfer theory and the water cloud model which essentially represents the extinction of microwave radiation as it passes through a layer of vegetation made up of elements containing water [27]. The first model (eq. 1) was a semi-empirical radiative transfer model of wave propagation through horizontal scattering and attenuating layer [14, 47].

$$\sigma_{for}^{\circ} = \sigma_{gr}^{\circ} e^{-\beta AGB} + \sigma_{veg}^{\circ} (1 - e^{-\beta AGB}) \quad (1)$$

where:

σ_{for}° - total forest backscatter

σ_{veg}° - backscatter from vegetation

σ_{gr}° - backscatter from ground

Although parameterization of such models is based on experimental data, the models do take into account (to a certain extent) the physical phenomena (e.g., scattering mechanisms, signal saturation, etc.). This first model, proposed in [14], has the advantage of allowing a straightforward inversion to estimate forest parameters (eq. 1). The total forest backscatter ($\sigma^{\circ}_{\text{for}}$) is modeled as the incoherent sum of direct and vegetation-attenuated ground scattering ($\sigma^{\circ}_{\text{gr}}$) and the direct scattering of the vegetation ($\sigma^{\circ}_{\text{veg}}$). The model takes into account the gaps in the canopy by weighing each term by the area fill factor expressed as a function of the stem-volume-dependent two-way forest transmissivity ($e^{-\beta\text{AGB}}$). The model does not take into account double bounce and higher order reflections, assuming that attenuation through the forest canopy is relevant (which might not be true for low biomass levels) and the forest floor is not perfectly flat. A more thorough description of model assumptions, parameterization and inversion is given in [14].

In contrast to the original formulation, in this paper, the two-way forest transmissivity was expressed as a function of biomass. Since stem volume can be transformed to biomass by multiplying with species dependent wood density, for the same moisture content, such a transformation would not affect the two-way forest transmissivity estimates. Furthermore, the total AGB includes the biomass of leaves, branches and twigs (i.e., the main tree elements interacting with L-band microwaves) therefore providing a better approximation of the total forest transmissivity (i.e., $e^{-\beta\text{AGB}}$ where β is an empirically defined coefficient in eq.1). Although the model was initially developed and tested for co-polarized waves it should be applicable to cross-polarized waves since the total backscatter is still a mixture of surface and volume scattering but of different magnitudes. The empirically derived forest transmissivity should compensate for differences in scattering mechanisms.

The other two forward models used (eq. 2 and 3) were proposed by [12] and respectively [24] and are loosely based on the water cloud approach.

$$\sigma^{\circ} = a - e^{-(b\text{AGB} + c)} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma^{\circ}_{(dB)} = a + (\sigma^{\circ}_{gr(dB)} - a) * e^{-(b\text{AGB})} \quad (3)$$

where:

$\sigma^{\circ}_{gr(dB)}$ - backscatter from ground

σ° - backscatter coefficient (linear or dB units)

a,b,c – model coefficients

The parameter a (i.e., the model asymptote) corresponds to the backscatter saturation point, whereas parameter b describes the gradient of the low biomass density part of the curve. Parameter c and the constant value $\sigma^{\circ}_{gr(dB)}$ describe the residual backscatter at zero biomass (i.e., the nominal backscatter from bare soil). The models are fitted using calibration data such that the sum of squared deviation from the theoretical curve is minimal. The advantage of such forward models is their robustness when limited samples are available and the potential for allowing residual backscatter at zero biomass density (i.e., allowing for soil surface scattering at low biomass levels) [12]. Model (3) assumes a fixed value for the ground backscatter (σ°_{gr}) which in this study was estimated as the average of all samples with biomass levels below 10 t/ha. Such sigmoid functions were often used to study the biomass–backscatter relationships, determine the dynamic range of the data and calculate the level of signal saturation [11, 12, 15, 24].

After model parameterization biomass was retrieved by analytically inverting models (1) to (3) as in:

$$AGB = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \left(\frac{\sigma^{\circ}_{veg} - \sigma^{\circ}_{for}}{\sigma^{\circ}_{veg} - \sigma^{\circ}_{gr}} \right) \quad \text{inversion function for (1)}$$

$$AGB = [-\ln(a - \sigma^{\circ}) - c]/b \quad \text{inversion function for (2)}$$

$$AGB = -\ln \frac{\sigma^{\circ(dB)-a}}{\sigma^{\circ}_{gr(dB)}} \times \frac{1}{b} \quad \text{inversion function for (3)}$$

When inverting, rules need to be defined for validation plots having backscatter values that fall outside of the modeled interval. The direct assignment of the minimum and maximum biomass values measured in the area of interest was proposed in [14] when the backscatter intensity values fall below or respectively above the modeled intervals. In this study, however, such values were simply discarded from inversion since our objective was not to produce a spatially explicit biomass map but

rather to analyze the errors of different retrieval models. Retaining such values would have defeated the purpose of the study since the estimation error would have been a function of the number and distribution of such outliers for each particular parameterization. The models were applied to all datasets and polarizations.

3.2.2 Backward parametric models

Three backward parametric models (eq. 4 to 6) were also used to retrieve biomass levels and their accuracy was estimated for each available study area and SAR image at both HH and HV polarizations. A dual-polarization model form was also used (eq. 6b) to assess the potential advantages of jointly using co- and cross-polarized information. Backward models have the advantage that regression coefficients estimation is straightforward and the statistical properties of the estimates are well understood.

$$AGB^\lambda = a + b\sigma_{(dB)}^o \quad (4)$$

$$AGB = ae^{b\sigma^o} \quad (5)$$

$$\log(AGB) = a + b\sigma_{(dB)}^o + c\sigma_{(dB)}^{o^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\log(AGB) = a + b\sigma_{xx}^o + c\sigma_{xx}^{o^2} + d\sigma_{xy}^o (dB) + e\sigma_{xy}^{o^2} (dB) \quad (6b)$$

where:

σ^o - backscatter coefficient (linear or dB units)

σ_{xy}^o - backscatter coefficient (dB units) for xy transmit/receive combination

a,b,c,d,e – model coefficients

$\lambda=0.5$

The linear model relating the squared root (or similar power) transformation of the biomass and the backscatter coefficient (eq.4) was proposed in [17]. The model form and the independent variables included were obtained after an iterative optimization process (see [17] for more details on model parameterization). For this study, the parameter λ proposed in [17] is used for single-polarized data.

The next model (eq.5) is an exponential type function. Such functions are frequently used to model biomass change with increasing backscatter [18, 23]. The model in eq. (6) was proposed by [48] and is based on backscattering information from fully polarized systems that provide independent measurements of forest structure and biomass. The quadratic form of the model reproduces the loss of radar backscatter sensitivity in higher biomass forests. The model has been adapted to work with single- and dual-polarized datasets by stripping out terms related to polarizations not acquired by the ALOS PALSAR sensor (eq. 6 and 6b). These modified models represent roughly one or two scattering mechanism depending on the polarization/s used (i.e., stem-surface / crown volume and crown volume scattering for HH and HV polarization, respectively).

The backward models were parameterized using least squares optimization and biomass retrieval was carried out over the entire validation dataset. It is noted that such models do not limit biomass retrieval based on defined backscatter thresholds which results in a biomass value being computed for each sample regardless of its backscatter.

3.2.3 Non-parametric models

Three non-parametric models (i.e., Ensemble Regression - ER, Random Forests - RF regression and Support Vector Machines regression - SVM) were used to estimate the biomass retrieval accuracy. Ensemble learning techniques use multiple models to improve the predictive power with respect to any of the constituent models by aggregating their predictions. Multiple models are generated based on the training dataset and subsequently pruned and integrated. The Least Square Boost (LSBoost) ensemble was used to incrementally build the ensemble by training new model instances using weak learners. The returned model structure was adjusted through 100 learning cycles and used in predicting responses to data. RF regression [49] uses similar ensemble learning methods by constructing a large number of decision trees from the training data which are subsequently used to derive overall predictions as the average response from all individually trained trees. Compared with ensemble and random forests regression, datasets used for SVM regression [50] need to be rescaled and modified to achieve accurate predictions. The produced model is also sensitive to the SVM

regression parameters. In this study, SVM regression was based on a radial basis kernel function (i.e., able to handle nonlinear relationships) and the related parameters were optimized by grid search. The values were scaled to the 0-1 interval prior to model construction. The non-parametric models were trained using single or dual polarization data as predictor variables and the observed AGB as the corresponding response. All models were parameterized using the entire biomass range and applied to the validation datasets to compute the biomass retrieval accuracy metrics.

3.3 Combined parametric models

To increase biomass estimation accuracy within the biomass intervals of interest (0-100 t/ha) while retaining the overall accuracy a combination of backward and forward parametric models was proposed. In the first instance both forward (e.g., model 1) and backward models (e.g., model 6) are parameterized and the biomass estimated independently. The biomass values obtained from the backward model are retained only within the physically realistic retrieval interval as parameterized by the forward model (e.g., σ_{veg}^o and σ_{gr}^o). A backscatter threshold corresponding to a user defined biomass level (e.g., 5, 10, 30 t/ha) is calculated based on the parameterized forward model. This backscatter threshold is subsequently used to retain the final biomass values: i) for backscatter values above the threshold the biomass estimates from the backward model are retained and, ii) for backscatter values below the threshold the biomass estimates from the forward model are retained. By changing the backscatter threshold the relative importance of the backward and respectively forward model for the final biomass estimation is controlled.

3.4 Error analysis

Cross-validation techniques are often used to compare the performance of different predictive models. Repeat random sub-sampling with cross-validation was used to assess biomass retrieval accuracy. To reduce variability due to random sampling effects, 25 rounds were performed by splitting the datasets into training (60%) and validation (40%) samples. During each round the models were parameterized based on the training samples and subsequently used to estimate the biomass of the validation samples. Biomass retrieval accuracy was described using four error metrics: the root mean squared

error (RMSE), the relative RMSE, the average error (bias) and the correlation coefficient (r) between measured and retrieved AGB. In addition, a relative estimation error ($RE_{\%}$) was calculated for each validation sample (eq. 7) and averaged by biomass intervals.

$$RE_{\%} = 100 * |AGB_{\text{observed}} - AGB_{\text{predicted}}| / AGB_{\text{observed}} \quad (7)$$

Although the relative error metric suffers from instability when approaching zero biomass values (i.e., as the denominator approaches zero the relative error approaches infinity) we consider its use valuable especially when assessing the biomass error by retrieval intervals where other metrics (i.e., absolute error) are less meaningful. For example, an absolute estimation error of 5 t/ha could be considered as acceptable for higher biomass intervals (e.g., 50-100 t/ha) but would represent a significant deviation from the true value at lower biomass intervals (e.g., 0-10 t/ha).

The error metrics for biomass estimation were computed for each SAR acquisition date and polarization from predicted and their corresponding observed values accumulated over the 25 iterations. Such averages provided a measure of model sensitivity to random sampling effects (i.e., the input training dataset). The standard deviation of the errors provided a measure of random sampling effects on the retrieval accuracy. In addition, the error metrics were averaged by study area (i.e., using all SAR acquisition dates) for the same polarization to provide a synopsis of the expected retrieval accuracy for each model. The standard deviation of the multi-temporal averages provided a measure of the temporal stability of the error metrics (i.e., a measure of changing environmental conditions effects).

IV. Results

In semi-arid environments a large part of the scattering comes from the forest floor (due to the open canopy structure and relatively low biomass levels) and the environmental conditions could strongly influence the scattering mechanisms. In this study images acquired during dry and wet periods were used to study the potential influence of such effects on the retrieval accuracy. The smaller extent (16 km²) of the Australian study site and the almost flat topography guaranteed little spatial variations in

the environmental conditions for each acquisition date. For the Spanish study site, however, such spatial variation could be present due to the considerably larger area (10,000 km²).

4.1 Analysis of the backscatter-biomass relationship

The relationship between radar backscatter and biomass density was assessed using six biomass intervals. The first interval (i.e., 0-10 t/ha) corresponds to sparsely vegetated areas where the ground contribution is large. The second and third intervals (i.e., 10-30 and 30-50 t/ha) correspond to an increasing proportion of the volume scattering and a reduction of the ground component due to signal attenuation whereas for the remaining intervals (i.e., 50-75, 75-100 and, >100 t/ha) the volume scattering component dominates and signal saturation appears. The above-ground biomass levels for the sites used in this study ranged between 1.5 and 145.6 t/ha, with most of the plots being below the maximum saturation limit of L-band estimated at 100 t/ha [3]. Fig. 2 reports the mean value and standard deviation of the backscatter for each biomass interval (dB) calculated for each dataset and polarization in both study areas. The spread of the measurements around the mean indicate backscatter heterogeneity due to surface characteristics (i.e., soil moisture and surface roughness), forest structure, vegetation water content and the sensitivity of the backscatter to AGB. The total dynamic range was between 4 and 6 dB for HH and HV polarization, respectively. However, the dynamic range between adjacent biomass intervals was significantly lower. The highest value, 2-3 dB, was recorded between the two lowest biomass intervals (0-10 and 10-30 t/ha). With increasing biomass the mean backscatter difference between subsequent classes decreases with the highest biomass classes being separated by less than 1 dB. The highest standard deviation (2.5 dB) was recorded for the lowest biomass interval for both polarizations which could be explained by a significant influence of the underlying surface properties. With increasing AGB the backscatter variability decreased to less than 0.5 dB for the highest biomass interval.

After rainfall events backscatter increases by up to 3 dB for HH polarization and 1 dB for HV polarization for the Australian study area (Fig. 2 left panel, 2010.07.05, Acc.Pp.=4.6 mm and 2010.08.20, Acc.Pp. 11.0 mm). For the Spanish study area backscatter levels after rainfall events increased by only 1 dB (Fig. 2 right panel, 2008.06.03, Acc.Pp.=20.6mm). The smaller increase was

likely caused by spatial patterns of rainfall due to the much larger area analyzed. Notably, rainfall events did not affect backscatter dynamic range and by-biomass-interval variability which was reflected in similar biomass retrieval accuracies regardless of the environmental conditions as demonstrated in the next sections. The estimated saturation point and biomass density below saturation computed as in [12] are presented in Table 2. Different saturation points were observed for the two study areas with higher values being recorded for the Spanish dataset. Such differences were explained by the generally higher backscatter levels at both polarizations observed for the Spanish datasets over forest or other land cover types. The biomass density below saturation was higher for the Australian study area by an average of 18 t/ha.

[Fig. 2 and Table 2 about here]

4.2 Error analysis for the entire biomass range

Daily RMSE for all SAR datasets are presented in Fig. 3 for single polarized models. For each day the RMSE was averaged over the 25 independent iterations. The standard deviation was calculated to provide a measure of results variability on the samples selected for model parameterization. The RMSE varied around 24 ± 1.9 t/ha and 21 ± 2.2 t/ha for the Australian and Spanish study areas, respectively, at both polarizations. When analyzed by model, the day to day change in RMSE was usually below 2 t/ha suggesting fairly stable retrieval accuracy regardless of the environmental conditions for both study areas. Small daily changes of the standard deviation (< 2 t/ha) also suggested that environmental conditions had little effect on biomass retrieval metrics. It is noted that similar results were obtained for the dual-polarization models (data not shown).

[Fig. 3 about here]

The low sensitivity of the RMSE to environmental effects suggested that overall error metrics could be computed for each area taking into account all SAR acquisition dates. Therefore, average values for RMSE, relative RMSE, r , and estimation bias were computed for each study area to provide a synopsis of the expected retrieval accuracy for each model (Fig. 4). No consistent trend was observed

among different models for RMSE and relative RMSE metrics. One model (model 3) appeared to consistently outperform all remaining models, though by small margins (3-4 t/ha and 7-10% lower for RMSE and respectively relative RMSE), in both study areas and for both polarizations. In general, the average relative RMSEs were between 40% and 80% which is comparable to previously reported results [8, 16]. More interesting trends were observed when analyzing the correlation between observed and predicted biomass (r). Forward models consistently provided the lowest r values in both study areas and for both polarizations. Average r values over both study areas and polarizations were 0.48 for the forward models, 0.61 for the backward models and 0.58 for the non-parametric models. Similar trends were observed for the estimation bias with the forward models having the highest bias. One model in particular, model 3, underestimated the biomass by an average of 10 t/ha. The smallest bias (<1.5 t/ha) was observed for the two non-parametric models based on ensemble regression (i.e., ER and RF). Using two polarizations consistently improved all error metrics although only by small margins. These results support previous findings [17, 35] which found no significant improvement in biomass estimation when using two polarized models. However, two-polarized non-parametric models (i.e., ER and RF) provided almost unbiased biomass estimates.

[Fig. 4 about here]

4.3 Error analysis by biomass intervals

The relative estimation error ($RE_{\%}$) was further studied by biomass intervals (Fig. 5). The highest estimation error was consistently associated with the lowest biomass interval (0-10 t/ha), despite its higher dynamic range. With increasing biomass the errors decreased significantly for biomass intervals around the saturation point after which the estimation error starts increasing. Similar results were obtained when simultaneously using two polarizations (Fig. 6). The higher relative estimation error observed for the lowest biomass interval could be the result of two factors: high signal variability due to the influence of local surface conditions (i.e., roughness and moisture) and the instability of the $RE_{\%}$ metric as explained in the previous section. Modeling studies showed that in low biomass areas direct scattering from the ground dominates the signal [51] with the volume

scattering having a much lesser role. The higher backscatter standard deviation for the lowest biomass interval (i.e., 0-10 t/ha) observed for our study areas (Fig. 2) support previous findings suggesting that biomass estimation errors in this interval depends mostly on the local surface conditions. Note that forward models provided lower estimation errors for the lowest biomass interval, partially due to the model inversion constraints which limit retrieval below a certain backscatter threshold (e.g., $\sigma_{\text{gr(dB)}}$, σ_{gr}). When using backward and non-parametric models, however, no constraints are imposed with biomass retrieval being carried out for all validation plots.

[Fig. 5 and 6 about here]

4.3 Error analysis for combined model retrieval

Fig. 7 presents the results of a combined retrieval method using initial estimates from forward (model 1) and backward (model 6) models. Similar results, not shown, were obtained when using other combinations of forward and backward models. A backscatter threshold corresponding to 10 t/ha was used to separate the backscatter values and retain the corresponding biomass estimates: for backscatter below the threshold, the biomass estimated from the forward model was retained while for backscatter above the threshold the biomass estimated by the backward model was retained. The improvement in retrieval accuracy was evident when compared to initial models, especially when looking at specific intervals. Using the combined approach the higher accuracy of the model proposed in [14] was largely retained for the lowest biomass levels (0-30 t/ha) while increasing the estimation accuracy for the higher biomass levels (30-100 t/ha) by around 10-20% with respect to the forward models. In addition, the overall error in the 10-100 t/ha interval was typically improved with respect to the forward model by 5-15%, depending on study area and polarization. One should notice, however, that such improvements come at the cost of discarding some of the backscatter values before retrieval. Therefore, such retrieval strategies would imply labeling pixels outside the modeled interval (as

estimated by forward models) as non retrievable which would result in patchy biomass maps. For our study areas the number of values discarded varied up to 25% of the total number of samples.

[Fig. 7 about here]

V. Discussions

Study areas with different species composition were selected, to assess if similar trends and estimation errors are obtained for a variety of situations and independently of the ground sampling strategy. Analyzing a relatively small forest (16 km²) with limited species variability (i.e., Australian site) allowed the exclusion of potential errors due to spatial variability in environmental conditions. The Spanish study area was instead characterized by species heterogeneity and spatial variability, since a regional sized dataset was used (10.000 km²).

The backscatter dynamic range for both study areas was lower when compared to values reported in [11] while it was close to the values reported in [17]. Note that backscatter dynamic range is significantly influenced by the selection of the low biomass sample plots. Frequently, such plots are located in non-forested areas such as bare agricultural fields which could present significantly lower backscatter due to reduced surface roughness which favors specular scattering. For both study areas more than two-thirds of the dynamic range corresponded to the lowest biomass interval (0-30 t/ha) while for the remaining interval (30-100 t/ha) the dynamic range was around 1-2 dB depending on polarization which could explain, to a certain extent, the difficulties encountered by many studies when retrieving biomass using L-band backscatter. The backscatter range at which signal saturation occurs was within previously reported intervals [11, 12] although such values are likely to fluctuate with sensor calibration and local conditions. The biomass density below saturation point was higher for the Australian study area (57 t/ha) when compared to the Spanish study area (39 t/ha). Nevertheless, both values were within previously observed ranges [11, 12, 24].

Reported biomass retrieval accuracy metrics are frequently limited to RMSE with fewer authors providing information on the relative RMSE, estimation bias or the correlation between predicted and observed values. Although RMSE is an important metric, by itself it is not sufficient for a

comprehensive error characterization. Relative RMSE provides additional information of estimation precision since the performance of models applied over variable biomass ranges could be more easily compared. Additional metrics such as the estimation bias and the correlation between predicted and observed values (r) could be useful for selecting the most appropriate model since different models could present similar RMSE or relative RMSE values (see Section IV). In this study, the observed RMSE was around 20 t/ha regardless of study area with relative RMSE varying around 40-50% for the Australian study area and 60-80% for the Spanish study area. The difference in relative RMSE values between the two study areas was attributed to the larger samples variability at the Spanish study site due to the increased number of species and the much larger area covered by the forest inventory (i.e., spatial variability of the environmental conditions). The correlation between observed and predicted values (r) was between 0.4-0.7 depending mostly on polarization and retrieval model. The estimation bias was generally below 5 t/ha except for model 3 which underestimated biomass level by an average 10 t/ha.

This study also showed that forest biomass retrieval accuracy from radar backscatter observations is highly variable within the L-band sensitivity range. In particular, considerably larger errors were observed for all models at both ends of the sensitivity interval – i.e., when approaching 0 and 100 t/ha. Despite the high backscatter dynamic range, forest biomass retrieval was most likely hindered by surface properties for the low biomass levels (i.e., < 30 t/ha). If surface properties are not taken into account incorrect estimation is expected in low biomass areas particularly for long wavelengths. For mid-range biomass intervals (30-75 t/ha) better retrieval accuracy (20-35%) was achieved by using backward parametric models with non-parametric and forward models providing slightly higher estimation errors (i.e., 30-40% and respectively 40-50%). At higher biomass levels (i.e., >100 t/ha) signal saturation could be overcome by using longer wavelengths. The use of P-band data could increase the saturation point to about 200 t/ha [3, 5] and thus increase the retrievable biomass interval. However, the higher penetration at P-band would also increase the surface scattering contribution to the total backscatter at mid range biomass densities. Without information on surface characteristics

from SAR or ancillary sensors, forest biomass retrieval in degraded or regenerating forests could bare significant errors.

Using forward semi-empirical models (e.g., model 1) the main scattering components can be estimated as well as the signal attenuation through the forest canopy which allows examination of the relative importance of ground and volume scattering components. A further advantage of such methods resides in the opportunity to limit the biomass retrieval to a physically valid backscatter interval which decreases the estimation error at low biomass levels. The main drawback of the semi-empirical and empirical forward models is the need for inverse relationships to retrieve biomass values. This has a significant influence on the retrieval errors since the model parameterization is based on least-squares regression which minimizes the sum of squared distances from each observation to the fitted line. Forward models parameterize the response in backscatter with increasing biomass hence, minimizing the errors of the response variable backscatter. For the backward models, however, this distance corresponds to the response variable AGB which explains the generally higher estimation accuracies (with the exception of the lowest biomass intervals). However, none of the studied models consistently outperformed the remaining ones when considering overall values for each error metric. Nonetheless, some general conclusions could be drawn since backward and non-parametric models consistently outperformed forward models when analyzing the correlation between predicted and observed values, while two of the non-parametric models (i.e. ER and RF) presented almost no estimation bias. When analyzing retrieval errors by biomass intervals it was evident that forward models were more accurate at low biomass levels while backward models showed considerably better results for intermediate biomass levels. The combined retrieval strategy proposed in this study has taken advantage of the different models strengths to decrease overall and by biomass intervals RMSE with up to 5-15% and respectively 10-20%. Such a retrieval strategy can be used to gear the retrieval towards obtaining the most accurate biomass estimate at either ends of the sensitivity spectrum depending on the specific application. For example, given a pre-existing classification, one could gear the algorithm for higher accuracies at low biomass intervals in re-

growth areas while maintaining high retrieval accuracies for the higher biomass levels in mature forests.

Parametric and non-parametric models implicitly incorporate the dielectric properties of the vegetation and the underlying surface [52]. Since these properties are known to vary in space and time, relationships derived for a specific dataset are not easily transferable – one of the major drawbacks of such retrieval methods. Even for similar environmental conditions (i.e., dry) significantly different model parameters were found between study areas, acquisition dates and polarizations which suggest that estimation errors would increase when applying models parameterized for different satellite datasets or regions. Numerical models [28, 29] have the potential to improve model transferability between areas by taking into account additional parameters such as surface properties and vegetation structural parameters (e.g., water content, leaves/branch orientation, etc.). Unfortunately, such detailed information is not readily available from existing field campaigns or forest inventories, and so has to be retrieved from independent sources. In addition, interactions between microwaves and media depend not only on the easier-to-generalize vegetation structural properties (e.g., length and orientation of branches, leaves shape and size, etc.), but also on the vegetation water content which changes along the canopy, thereby partly explaining the relatively low prediction accuracy (RMSE of 1.5 to 8 dB for HH and HV polarization respectively) obtained from such approaches. With a dynamic range for dense vegetation (i.e., > 30 t/ha) of only 2-3 dB, the numerical models lack the accuracy needed for forest biomass retrieval making parametric and non-parametric models still relevant for the remote sensing community.

When compared to previous studies the results were often divergent. For example, in [14] the first model (model 1) was used to retrieve biomass from L-band HH data over coniferous dominated boreal forests with estimation accuracy metrics ranging between 36-102 t/ha (RMSE), 25-51% (relative RMSE) and 0.56-0.87 (r). While the RMSE observed in this study was considerably lower most likely due to the lower biomass levels, the relative RMSE and r metrics were slightly worse. The reduced accuracy could be related to the smaller sample size (i.e., 0.25 ha) used in this study when compare to the significantly larger sample plots (i.e., 0.5 to 20 ha or larger) used in [14]. Smaller

sampling plots are related to an increased forest variability which in turn negatively affects biomass retrieval accuracy since similar backscatter values could stem largely from different forest structures. In [17], a linear model (model 4) was used to retrieve biomass over hemiboreal coniferous forests while in [18] an exponential model (model 5) was used over tropical forest. The RMSE and relative RMSE observed were around 70-80 t/ha and 40-45% (HH and HV polarizations) for the hemiboreal forests. For the tropical forests the RMSE ranged from 100 to 150 t/ha with a negative bias around 50 t/ha. Again, the much higher RMSE observed in these studies was most likely related to mean biomass values in excess of 150 t/ha. It is noted that it is difficult to pinpoint the origin of results incongruence even when applying the same model since previous studies were carried out over forests greatly exceeding the widely acknowledged L-band biomass sensitivity interval (i.e., <100 t/ha), using plots of varying size and with reference data of variable accuracies (i.e., up to 95 t/ha estimation error for reference biomass values [18]). In addition, for the forward models rules have to be decided for backscatter values outside of the retrievable interval which further distort the error metrics and thus any comparison.

In earlier studies, radar backscatter was shown to provide better relationships with biomass levels at coarser spatial resolution and/or within a multi-temporal approach [53, 54]. Such studies demonstrated that SAR-based biomass retrieval could achieve the precision required for global, continental or regional scale (i.e., boreal or tropical region) applications. The relatively high accuracy obtained in such studies was related to the low spatial resolutions at which such regional maps are produced (1 to 10 km pixel spacing), which dramatically improves the accuracy of both the backscatter coefficient estimates (i.e., high number of looks) and field biomass sampling (i.e., decreased forest variability). The approach described in [54] could be applied to the wealth of SCANSAR data available from ALOS PALSAR, but such an approach would produce appropriate results only when estimates at coarse spatial resolution are required. However, for forest management purposes high spatial resolution (i.e., 100 m pixel spacing or better) products are necessary, since forest stands can be as small as 1 ha in highly fragmented areas. The results here have shown that relatively high estimation accuracy (down to 20%) can be achieved at plot level at least for some

biomass intervals. At stand level, improvements of the estimation errors are expected since such analysis would benefit from the smaller errors associated to lower forest spatial variability, decreased speckle, and more accurate field estimates since larger areas proved to be less prone to errors due to expansion of field measured forest parameters.

VI. Conclusions

This paper analyzed the SAR backscatter response from two forested areas located in semi-arid environments, and studied overall and by interval biomass retrieval errors using a range of parametric and non-parametric models. The sensitivity of L-band radar backscatter to variations in above-ground biomass over areas of similar environmental conditions but with different forest species composition and field sampling strategies were explored, demonstrating that our findings were not of random nature but genuine trends independent of the local conditions. For both study areas, the backscatter coefficient increased asymptotically with biomass from the minimum values associated with sparsely vegetated areas. Although overall dynamic ranges varied within expected values, different trends were observed when analyzing by biomass intervals, with most of the dynamic range corresponding to low biomass intervals. For the remaining biomass intervals up to the L-band saturation point the backscatter dynamic range was considerably smaller, which explains the difficulties encountered by many authors when estimating biomass levels using L-band radar data.

This study also showed that retrieval accuracy of forest biomass from L-band radar backscatter observations is highly variable when different biomass intervals are considered. In particular, larger errors were observed at both ends of the L-band biomass sensitivity interval. At very low biomass levels information on surface properties is needed to increase the estimation accuracy, whereas at higher biomass levels signal saturation dominates and the estimation accuracy starts to degrade.

Overall, biomass retrieval errors were largely similar for the entire range of parametric and non-parametric models studied. However, forward models consistently provided the lowest correlation between observed and predicted biomass while non-parametric models generally provided unbiased estimation. When analyzing by-biomass intervals forward models consistently outperformed

backward and non-parametric models at low biomass levels (i.e., < 30 t/ha) while at intermediate biomass levels (30-75 t/ha) backward models were the most accurate (relative RMSE 20-35%) closely followed by non-parametric models. To increase biomass retrieval accuracy, a strategy based on combining different model types was proposed. Such a retrieval strategy had the potential to reduce both overall and by-biomass interval errors by up to 15-20%.

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References

- [1] H. K. Gibbs, S. Brown, J. O. Niles, and J. A. Foley, "Monitoring and estimating tropical forest carbon stocks: making REDD a reality," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 2, pp. 1-13, 2007.
- [2] J. Riom and T. Le Toan, " Relations entre des types de forêts de pins maritimes et la rétrodiffusion radar en bande L," *Proc. Spectral Signatures of Objects in Remote Sensing Symposium* Avignon, France, 1981.
- [3] M. C. Dobson, T. Ulaby, T. Le Toan, A. Beaudoin, and E. S. Kasischke, "Dependence of radar backscatter on coniferous forest biomass," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 30 pp. 412-415, 1992.
- [4] E. S. Kasischke, N. L. Christensen, and B. J. Stocks, "Fire, Global Warming, and the Carbon Balance of Boreal Forests," *Ecological Applications*, vol. 5, pp. 437-451, 1995.
- [5] E. J. Rignot, J. Way, C. Williams, and L. Viereck, "Radar Estimates of Aboveground Biomass in Boreal Forests of Interior Alaska," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 32, pp. 1117-1124, 1994.
- [6] T. Le Toan, A. Beaudoin, and D. Guyon, "Relating forest biomass to SAR data," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 30, pp. 403-411, 1992.
- [7] P. A. Harrell, L. L. Bourgeau-Chavez, E. S. Kasischke, N. H. F. French, and N. L. Christensen, "Sensitivity of ERS-1 and JERS-1 Radar Data to Biomass and Stand Structure in Alaskan Boreal Forest," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 54, pp. 247-260, 1995.
- [8] P. A. Harrell, E. S. Kasischke, L. L. Bourgeau-Chavez, E. M. Haney, and N. L. Christensen, "Evaluation of Approaches Aboveground Biomass in Using SIR-C Data to Estimating Southern Pine Forests " *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 59, pp. 223-233, 1997.
- [9] M. L. Imhoff, "Radar Backscatter and Biomass Saturation: Ramifications for Global Biomass Inventory," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, pp. 511-518, 1995.
- [10] E. S. Kasischke, N. L. Christensen, and L. L. Bourgeau-Chavez, "Correlating Radar Backscatter with Components of Biomass in Loblolly Pine Forests," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, pp. 643-659, 1995.

- [11] R. Lucas, J. Armston, R. Fairfax, R. Fensham, A. Accad, J. Carreiras, J. Kelley, P. Bunting, D. Clewley, S. Bray, D. Metcalfe, J. Dwyer, M. Bowen, T. Eyre, M. Laidlaw, and M. Shimada, "An Evaluation of the ALOS PALSAR L-Band Backscatter—Above Ground Biomass Relationship Queensland, Australia: Impacts of Surface Moisture Condition and Vegetation Structure," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observation and Remote Sensing*, vol. 3, pp. 576-593, 2010.
- [12] A. J. Luckman, "The Effects of Topography on Mechanism of Radar Backscatter from Coniferous Forest and Upland Pasture," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 36, pp. 1830-1834, 1998.
- [13] J. T. Pulliainen, L. Kurvonen, and M. T. Hallikainen, "Multitemporal Behavior of L- and C-Band SAR Observations of Boreal Forests," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 37, pp. 927-937, 1999.
- [14] M. Santoro, L. Eriksson, J. Askne, and C. Schmullius, "Assessment of stand-wise stem volume retrieval in boreal forest from JERS-1 L-band SAR backscatter " *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, pp. 3425-3454, 2006.
- [15] A. Luckman, J. Baker, T. M. Kuplich, C. D. F. Yanasse, and A. C. Frery, "A study of the relationship between radar backscatter and regenerating tropical forest biomass for spaceborne SAR instruments," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 60, pp. 1-13, 1997.
- [16] E. J. Rignot, J. Way, C. Williams, L. Viereck, and J. Yarie, "P-band radar mapping of forest biomass in boreal forests of interior Alaska," *Proc. Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 1994. IGARSS '94. Proceedings. 1994 IEEE International Pasadena, CA, USA, 1994.*
- [17] G. Sandberg, L. M. H. Ulander, J. E. S. Fransson, J. Holmgren, and T. L. Toan, "L- and P-band backscatter intensity for biomass retrieval in hemiboreal forest," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 115, pp. 2874-2886, 2011.
- [18] S. Enghart, V. Keuck, and F. Siegert, "Aboveground biomass retrieval in tropical forests — The potential of combined X- and L-band SAR data use," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 115, pp. 1260-1271, 2011.
- [19] J. M. Kellndorfer, M. C. Dobson, J. D. Vona, and M. Clutter, "Toward Precision Forestry: Plot-Level Parameter Retrieval for Slash Pine Plantations With JPL AIRSAR," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 41, pp. 1571-1582, 2003.
- [20] K. J. Ranson, S. Saatchi, and G. Sun, "Boreal Forest Ecosystem Characterization with SIR-C/XSAR," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, pp. 867-876, 1995.
- [21] T. Le Toan, S. Quegan, I. Woodward, M. Lomas, N. Delbart, and G. Picard, "Relating radar remote sensing of biomass to modelling of forest carbon budgets," *Climatic change*, vol. 67, pp. 379-402, 2004.
- [22] R. M. Lucas, A. K. Milne, N. Cronin, C. Witte, and R. Denham, "The potential of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) for quantifying the biomass of Australia's woodlands," *The Rangeland Journal*, vol. 22, pp. 124-140, 2000.
- [23] S. Moreau and T. Le Toan, "Biomass quantification of Andean wetland forages using ERS satellite SAR data for optimizing livestock management," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 84, pp. 477-492, 2003.
- [24] R. M. Lucas, N. Cronin, A. Lee, M. Moghaddam, C. Witte, and P. Tickle, "Empirical relationships between AIRSAR backscatter and LiDAR-derived forest biomass, Queensland, Australia," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 100, pp. 407-425, 2006.
- [25] D. Lu, "The potential and challenge of remote sensing-based biomass estimation," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, pp. 1297-1328, 2006

- [26] J. T. Pulliainen, P. J. Mikkela, M. T. Hallikainen, and J.-P. Ikonen, "Seasonal Dynamics of C-Band Backscatter of Boreal Forests with Applications to Biomass and Soil Moisture Estimation," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 34, pp. 758-770, 1996.
- [27] E. P. W. Attema and F. T. Ulaby, "Vegetation modeled as a water cloud," *Radio Science*, vol. 13, pp. 357-364, 1978.
- [28] M. Burgin, D. Clewley, R. Lucas, and M. Moghaddam, "A Generalized Radar Backscattering Model Based on Wave Theory for Multilayer Multispecies Vegetation," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 49, pp. 4832-4845, 2011.
- [29] R. Lucas, M. Moghaddam, and N. Cronin, "Microwave Scattering From Mixed-Species Forests, Queensland, Australia," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 42, pp. 2142-2159, 2004.
- [30] M. Neumann, S. S. Saatchi, L. M. H. Ulander, and J. E. S. Fransson, "Assessing Performance of L- and P-Band Polarimetric Interferometric SAR Data in Estimating Boreal Forest Above-Ground Biomass," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 50, pp. 714-726, 2012.
- [31] A. C. Morel, S. S. Saatchi, Y. Malhi, N. J. Berry, L. Banin, D. Burslem, R. Nilus, and R. C. Ong, "Estimating aboveground biomass in forest and oil palm plantation in Sabah, Malaysian Borneo using ALOS PALSAR data," *Forest Ecology and Management*, vol. 262, pp. 1786-1798, 2011.
- [32] T. Svoray, M. Shoshany, P. J. Curran, G. M. Foody, and A. Perevolotsky, "Relationship between green leaf biomass volumetric density and ERS-2 SAR backscatter of four vegetation formations in the semi-arid zone of Israel," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 22, pp. 1601-1607, 2001.
- [33] J. N. Collins, L. B. Hutley, R. J. Williams, G. Boggs, D. Bell, and R. Bartolo, "Estimating landscape-scale vegetation carbon stocks using airborne multi-frequency polarimetric synthetic aperture radar (SAR) in the savannahs of north Australia," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 30, pp. 1141-1159, 2009.
- [34] J. R. Santos, M. S. P. Lacruz, L. S. Araujo, and M. Keil, "Savanna and tropical rainforest biomass estimation and spatialization using JERS-1 data," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 23, pp. 1217-1229, 2002.
- [35] E. T. A. Mitchard, S. S. Saatchi, I. H. Woodhouse, G. Nangendo, N. S. Ribeiro, M. Williams, C. M. Ryan, S. L. Lewis, T. R. Feldpausch, and P. Meir, "Using satellite radar backscatter to predict above-ground woody biomass: a consistent relationship across four different African landscapes.," *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol. 36, pp. 1-6, 2009.
- [36] N. L. R. Cronin, "The potential of airborne polarimetric synthetic aperture radar data for quantifying and mapping the biomass and structural diversity of woodlands in semiarid Australia," The University of New South Wales, Sydney, 2004.
- [37] T. Castel, A. Beaudoin, N. Stach, N. Stussi, T. L. Toan, and P. Durand, "Sensitivity of space-borne SAR data to forest parameters over sloping terrain. Theory and experiment," *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 22, pp. 2351-2376, 2001.
- [38] S. Tebaldini and F. Rocca, "Multibaseline Polarimetric SAR Tomography of a Boreal Forest at P- and L-Bands," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 50, pp. 232-246, 2012.
- [39] G. Montero, R. Ruiz-Peinado, and M. Muñoz, *Produccion de biomasas y fijacion de CO2 por los bosques españoles*. Madrid: Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnologia, 2005.
- [40] W. H. Burrows, M. B. Hoffman, J. F. Compton, and P. V. Back, "Allometric relationships and community biomass stocks in White Cypress Pine (*Callitris glaucophylla*) and associated eucalypts of the Carnarvon area, central Queensland.," 2001.

- [41] S. D. Hamilton, G. Brodie, and C. O'Dwyer, "Allometric relationships for estimating biomass in grey box (*Eucalyptus microcarpa*)," *Australian Forestry*, vol. 68, pp. 267-273, 2005.
- [42] M. Shimada, O. Isoguchi, T. Tadono, and K. Isono, "PALSAR Radiometric and Geometric Calibration," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 47, pp. 3915-3932, 2009.
- [43] L. Jong-Sen, "Digital Image Enhancement and Noise Filtering by Use of Local Statistics," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 2, pp. 165-168, 1980.
- [44] O. Frey, M. Santoro, C. L. Werner, and U. Wegmüller, "DEM-Based SAR Pixel-Area Estimation for Enhanced Geocoding Refinement and Radiometric Normalization," *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, IEEE*, vol. 10, pp. 48-52, 2013.
- [45] U. Wegmüller, C. Werner, T. Strozzi, and A. Wiesmann, "Automated and precise image registration procedures," in *Analysis of multi-temporal remote sensing images*, vol. 2, L. Bruzzone and P. Smits, Eds. Singapore: World Scientific 2002, 2002, pp. 37-49.
- [46] M. A. Tanase, R. Panciera, K. Lowell, C. Aponte, J. M. Hacker, and J. P. Walker, "Forest Biomass Estimation at High Spatial Resolution: Radar vs. Lidar sensors," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, vol. PP, pp. 1-5, in press.
- [47] J. Askne, P. Dammert, J. Fransson, H. Israelsson, and L. M. H. Ulander, "Retrieval of forest parameters using intensity and repeat-pass interferometric SAR information," *Proc. Retrieval of Bio- and Geophysical Parameters from SAR Data for Land Applications*, Toulouse, 1995.
- [48] S. Saatchi, K. Halligan, D. G. Despain, and R. L. Crabtree, "Estimation of Forest Fuel Load From Radar Remote Sensing," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 45, pp. 1726-1739, 2007.
- [49] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, pp. 5-32, 2001.
- [50] B. E. Boser, I. Guyon, and V. Vapnik., "A training algorithm for optimal margin classifiers," *Proc. Proceedings of the Fifth Annual Workshop on Computational Learning Theory*, 1992.
- [51] J. J. van Zyl, "Unsupervised Classification of Scattering Behavior Using Radar Polarimetry Data," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 27, pp. 36-45, 1989.
- [52] M. C. Dobson, F. T. Ulaby, L. E. Pierce, T. L. Sharik, K. M. Bergen, J. Kellndorfer, J. R. Kendra, Y. C. L. E. Li, A. Nashashibi, K. Sarabandi, and P. Siqueira, "Estimation of Forest Biophysical Characteristics in Northern Michigan with SIR-C/X-SAR," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 33, pp. 877-895, 1995.
- [53] S. Saatchi, R. A. Houghton, A. Dos Santos, J. V. Soares, and Y. Yu, "Distribution of aboveground live biomass in the Amazon basin," *Glob. Change Biol.*, vol. 13, pp. 816-837, 2007.
- [54] M. Santoro, C. Beer, O. Cartus, C. Schmullius, A. Shvidenko, I. McCallum, U. Wegmüller, and A. Wiesmann, "Retrieval of growing stock volume in boreal forest using hyper-temporal series of Envisat ASAR ScanSAR backscatter measurements," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 115, pp. 490-507, 2011.

Fig. 1 Location of forest inventory plots for Spanish (left) and Australian (right) study areas, with background of ALOS PALSAR images acquired on 2008.07.19 (left) and 2010.05.20 (right). The insert in the left panel shows the general location of the Spanish study area. The inserts in the right panel show: the general location of the Australian study area (left), the reference biomass levels obtained from lidar data with the random plots used for data extraction (center) and a typical sampling site with the sampled trees distribution by forest layer (right). Only plots located on flat or near flat areas are shown for the Spanish study area.

Fig. 2 Average L-band radar backscatter by biomass intervals for Australian (left panel) and Spanish (right panel) study areas. The vertical bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

Fig. 3 Biomass estimation error (RMSE) for each SAR dataset for Australian (left panels) and Spanish (right panels) study area. Upper panels show HH polarization while bottom panels show HV polarization.

Fig. 4 Model depended estimation error metrics (RMSE, relative RMSE, r and Bias). The metrics are given for each model and polarization for the Australian (left) and Spanish (right) study areas. The values represent averages of all SAR acquisition dates. The vertical bars represent the standard deviation amongst individual days. Two equations were used produce the result labeled Model 6: single polarized models were based on eq. 6 while dual-polarized models were based on eq. 6b which adds two terms corresponding to the second polarization.

Fig. 5 Relative biomass estimation error (RE%) by biomass intervals for single polarized (HH polarization) models for the Australian (left panel) and Spanish (right panel) study areas. The values represent averages of all SAR acquisition dates.

Fig. 6 Relative biomass estimation error (RE%) by biomass intervals for dual polarized models. Australian study area-left panel and Spanish study area-right panel. The values represent averages of all SAR acquisition dates. The results labeled Model 6 were based on eq. 6b.

Fig. 7 Relative biomass estimation error (RE%) using a combined model for the Australian study area. Left panel represents HH polarization and right panel represent HV polarization. The values represent averages of all SAR acquisition dates.

Table 1 SAR data characteristics, processing parameters and main weather parameters. For the Spanish region the precipitation recorded at three meteorological stations (located near the north, the centre and respectively the south of the study area) are shown whereas the minimum and the maximum temperature is the average for the three stations.

Parameter	Value	
	Spain	Australia
Study area		
SAR acquisition date / Scene number	2007.07.17 - KC12666N55N38 2008.06.03 - KC19666N54N38 2008.07.19 - KC20666N57N38	2010.04.04 - ALPSRP223396480 2010.05.20 - ALPSRP230106480 2010.07.05 - ALPSRP236816480 2010.08.20 - ALPSRP243526480
Processing level	L1.5 (slant range intensity)*	L1.1 (complex data)
Acquisition mode	Fine Beam Dual (HH & HV polarizations)	
Multi-look factors	4 range x 16 azimuth	
Pixel spacing map geometry	50m UTM30N/ED1950	50m UTM55S/WGS84
Acc. Pp. (mm)**	[0.0/0.0/0.0], [20.9/20.4/20.4], [0.0/1.1/4.6]	[0.0], [0.0], [4.6], [11.0]
Max/min T (C°)	[33.1/11.4], [19.4/7.7], [34.0/14.3]	[26.8/16.3], [19.3/2.9], [12.7/1.7], [12.7/2.6]

*Format provided for Kyoto & Carbon Initiative / ** Accumulated precipitations recorded for the last 4 days before satellite overpass.

Table 2 Saturation point and biomass density below saturation point for Australian and Spanish study areas. The values were computed as in [12] and represent averages for all SAR acquisition dates.

Area	SAR metric	Saturation point (dB)	Biomass density 0.5 dB below saturation (t/ha)
Australia	HH	-8.9	56.1 ±1.6
	HV	-17.1	58.6 ±1.4
Spain	HH	-6.9	35.6 ±1.1
	HV	-12.2	43.1 ±1.0